

Psychoanalysis of Barrack Obama

By Edwin Amuga

The analysis of the life of the former United States president reveals some psychological aspects that might have contributed to his rise to becoming the first African-American President. Ann Dunham, Obama's mother, married a Kenyan man, Obama's father in 1961 who abandoned the family after three years in the form of a divorce. The Obama senior went to the reputable and famous Harvard University and studied economics and returned to his country to become a senior official of the Kenyan government. The mother in 1967 got married to another man, an Indonesian. She has later divorced again after which she embarked on globetrotting, from Hawaii to Indonesia to Pakistan. Sometimes she would leave her young son behind and sometimes took him with her.

What happened to the would-be president of the United States is the developed the oedipal complex from his childhood experiences. The male child was fixated on his mother and competed with his father for her attention (Chasseguet-Smirgel). After the divorce, the mother seemed fixated on other men as she was traveling occasionally leaving the young male child

behind. The critical point of awakening occurred when Obama realized that the mother had affections for others besides him, the paternal stand-ins who he continued with the fight for the mother's attention after divorce with the Kenyan. It dawned on him that he would never fully bond with his mother. The result is resentment towards women and emulating them; a thing he would never get beyond. The president's life demonstrates the psychosexual development stages, fear of loss of love, Oedipus complex, castration anxiety, and tripartite structure of personality that are responsible for his life achievements. Specific incidents and relationships in the former US president's life are analyzed from a Freudian psychoanalytic perspective to complete this purpose adequately.

The president's Oedipus complex manifested in his dream of becoming the president of the United States which his mother sedulously fostered in him. The Former President's taste for Mitchell Obama, a strong-willed lady-a man-like trait, and the systematic domination of his childhood life by his mother can be interpreted as projected fears and desires of his childhood.

Obama's life and achievements can also be analyzed using the alderman power-complex theoretical framework. Obama was encouraged and psychologically motivated to study hard and end up in one of the world's best universities so that he can do greater things than his father did. This burning desire to succeed beyond the father's achievement can be interpreted as trying to prove to the mother that he is a better man than those she got involved with as his father. He seemed to have many competitors and was more interested in ruling his 'mother's world' than being in sexual relationships. This is the psychological origin of the dream of becoming the president of the United States. His thoughts as a child were not primarily concerned with the growing number of men that his mother dated but rather about the prospects of potential competitors since his mother was also a high-profile woman, an anthropologist, and attracted men of that caliber and above (Chasseguet-Smirgel). The fears and wishes in Obama's life, including castration fear and the sex, wish for his mother in the form of jealousy against his father, the wish to outdo his father's achievements, legacy, and superiority and the loss of love fear and the wish to rise above his competitors (Klein, 2018). This is the genesis of Obama's power complex which is consistent with drive/structure theory.

There is a vast range of existing historical data suggesting that Obama's structure of behavior and personality are results of his Oedipus complex that was left unresolved that his mother instilled in him in the form of self-confidence and ambition, his character's narcissist and anal-sadistic organization, and his unconscious wish to attract his mother. It can, therefore, be said that those suffering from the Oedipus complex have an unconscious chance of achieving great things in life as seen in Obama and Alexander the Great (Klein, 2018).

References

- Klein, M. (2018). The Oedipus complex in the light of early anxieties (1945). In *The Oedipus complex today* (pp. 11–82). Routledge.
- Chasseguet-Smirgel, J. (2018). Feminine guilt and the Oedipus complex. In *Female sexuality* (pp. 94–134). Routledge.

